

1 **Time evolution of the mineral carbonation of ceramic bricks in a simulated**
2 **pilot plant using a common clay as sealing material at superficial**
3 **conditions**

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8 **Abstract**

9 Carbon dioxide is the most important anthropogenic greenhouse gas having
10 increased around 40% from the preindustrial period. Technological proposals
11 including carbon capture and storage procedures, especially the mineral
12 carbonation of CO₂, have been evaluated to prevent or reduce carbon dioxide
13 emission.

14 This research explores the possibility for CO₂ sequestration on ceramic brick
15 materials. A pilot-scale reaction chamber has been designed to mimic the
16 carbonation process in an abandoned quarry. The filling materials are ceramic
17 bricks and other construction with materials. The rubble is covered with common
18 clay to seal the reaction sites.

19 Bricks are composed of quartz, diopside, wollastonite and orthoclase, and minor
20 anhydrite. The common clay (marl) contains calcite, quartz, illite, smectite, and
21 kaolinite. Room temperature reaction were conducted at 0.5 bar constant
22 pressure, 4:1 solid/water. The reaction time was 5, 7, 9 and 12 months.

23 With the CO₂ treatment, wollastonite, diopside, and anhydrite were practically
24 destroyed at 12 months and calcite precipitated as a new phase in the bricks

25 carbonation. With increased reaction time macro- and meso-porosity decreased.
26 The micro- and nano-porosity increased due to closure of bigger pores because
27 of carbonate precipitation. Calcite increased in the common clay with reaction
28 time near the top of the reaction vessel. It can be linked to the observed migration
29 of moisture from the bricks to clay layers with the transport of carbonic acid and
30 Ca ions for subsequent precipitation of calcite. The pilot investigation supports
31 the proportion that brick waste can be used to sequester carbon.

32

33 **Keywords:** Mineral carbonation, mineral sequestration, carbon capture and
34 storage, ceramic bricks, common clay, sealing rock.

35

36 **1. Introduction**

37 Given the high global demand for energy, carbon dioxide emissions into the
38 atmosphere are of concern, leading to international attempts to establish
39 measures to control these emissions. International protocols have been
40 established to reduce the concentrations of these greenhouse gases (GHGs) that
41 cause global warming.

42 Improvements in energy use efficiency or reductions in the use of fossil fuels will
43 reduce the production of these gases. CO₂ storage and capture technologies
44 (CCS) will contribute to the stable and safe containment of this gas on a
45 permanent basis.

46 Mineral carbonation, or mineral sequestration, of CO₂ was proposed by Seifritz
47 (1990) as a process that occurs naturally from weathering of silicate rocks in a

48 CO₂-rich environment. These natural processes take place on a geological scale
49 of time. Of the alkaline earth metals, calcium and magnesium are by far the most
50 common in nature. Large quantities of industrial minerals and industrial wastes
51 rich in alkaline oxides are available for CO₂ fixation. Because of their abundance
52 calcium and magnesium are generally selected for the sequestration of mineral
53 CO₂.

54 The carbonation reactions of calcium and magnesium oxides are strongly
55 exothermic as the carbonate state is a low carbon energy state (Lackner et al.,
56 1995):

59 However, the most common form in nature of calcium and magnesium is in the
60 form of silicate minerals versus the binary oxides of these elements. The silicates
61 readily become carbonates since the silica present in these minerals is easily
62 interchangeable with carbonate ions. In general, the silicates reaction is (Huijgen
63 and Comans, 2003):

66 These reactions are still exothermic, but to a lesser extent than carbonation of
67 pure oxides. As stated above, these naturally occurring processes require long
68 periods of time.

69 That is why many investigators have gone towards accelerating this procedure.
70 The wet route is one of the acceleration techniques since the presence of water

93 (Galán and Aparicio, 2014). However, the main drawbacks of using these natural
94 materials are the extraction of the material, mining, and transport to the treatment
95 plant.

96 Readily available alternative sources to natural minerals that may be rich in
97 calcium or magnesium are industrial by-products or alkaline solid waste (Costa
98 et al., 2007; Dri et al., 2014; Huntzinger et al., 2009; Li et al., 2007; Mayoral et
99 al., 2013; Pan et al., 2012; Santos et al., 2013; Sipilä et al., 2008; Soong et al.,
100 2006; Uibua et al., 2011). These materials are an economical source of mineral
101 raw material for carbonation. In addition, their use reduces the environmental
102 impact of the waste materials by providing a second useful use for them. Unlike
103 natural materials, these wastes do not need to be extracted from the mine, many
104 of them are in an appropriate particle size range avoiding intensive grinding and
105 are generally found in industrial areas where carbonation treatment centers could
106 be located thus significantly reducing transportation costs.

107 Narahariseti et al. (2019) list optimal materials for mineral carbonation, including
108 industrial waste such as blast furnace slag, steel or general metallurgical waste
109 (Bacocchi et al., 2006; Gao et al., 2018; Ghacham et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2016;
110 Liu et al., 2018; Rushendra Revathy et al., 2016; Siriwardena and Peethamparan,
111 2015; Tamilselvi Dananjayan et al., 2016; Ukwattage et al., 2017), concrete or
112 cement residues (Ben Ghacham et al., 2015; D. R. Han et al., 2015; Kim et al.,
113 2017), carbide slag (Altiner, 2018; Gopinath and Mehra, 2016), fly ash (S. J. Han
114 et al., 2015; Hosseini et al., 2016; Jaschik et al., 2016; Mazzella et al., 2016; Park
115 et al., 2016), waste in soda ash plant (Zhao et al., 2017), among other possible
116 materials and possible uses of the product resulting from carbonation.

117

118 The main objective of this study was to investigate the process of mineral
119 carbonation by the wet process with bricks used in construction. For this purpose,
120 the situation will be simulated in which these bricks are used as filler in a disused
121 clay quarry in which CO₂ is injected for sequestration under conditions of ambient
122 temperature and pressure. The evolution of carbonation over time will be
123 evaluated, as well as the interaction of CO₂ with clay as a sealing rock.

124

125 **2. Materials and methods**

126

127 **2.1. Raw materials and experimental procedure**

128 The raw material, a ceramic brick (AUC1), is composed of quartz, diopside,
129 wollastonite and orthoclase and minor anhydrite. The clay used as sealing
130 material during the carbonation test contains calcite, quartz, illite, smectite and
131 kaolinite and a trace of dolomite. The clay mineral composition agrees with the
132 chemical composition.

133

134 In previous studies, the starting material was widely characterized (Martín et al.,
135 2018a, 2018b) as well as the employed reactor (Fig. 1) and the experimental
136 conditions were described, being a novelty in this study the variable reaction time.

137

138 Figure 1. Scheme of the reaction chamber designed for CO₂ brick reaction. The
139 brick layer is yellow and the marl is light gray (font view) and sampling cores at
140 5, 7, 9 and 12 months (top view).

141

142 The brick was ground in a jaw crusher and sieved in the laboratory. The 80% of
143 the sample was represented by fraction larger than 1 mm (Table 1).

144

145 Table 1. Granulometric fractions of the crusher sample (wt%).

146

147 The reaction conditions were: 0.5 bar constant pressure controlled by a mass
148 flow controller, 4:1 solid/water ratio and room temperature. The reaction time was
149 variable between 5 months to 12 months (5, 7, 9 and 12 months). After each
150 period, a sample was withdrawn and the core obtained was cut perpendicular to
151 its length into five cm-thick sections. The first five sections from the top
152 correspond to the upper marl (clay) layer, the next is the brick, and the last
153 corresponds to the marl at the bottom.

154

155 **2.2. Characterization and carbonation process tracing**

156 The mineralogical composition of tested samples was determined by X-ray
157 diffraction (XRD) using a D8 Advance (Bruker, Germany) diffractometer with
158 monochromatic Cu K α radiation produced at 40 kV and 30 mA. Ni filters and a
159 Lynexe detector were employed. Scanning was performed with a 0.015° 2 θ step
160 at 0.1 s per step from 3° to 70°. Rietveld refinement was realized to determine
161 the quantitative composition of untreated and treated bricks; in this case,
162 scanning was performed with a 0.015° 2 θ step size at 0.5 s per step between 3

163 and 120° adding corundum as the internal standard. The software used was
164 Profex (version 3.14.0) (Doebelin and Kleeberg, 2015).

165 The major element composition measured on glass discs was performed by X-
166 ray fluorescence (XRF) with an automated Panalytical Axios model spectrometer.

167 Carbonate content was determined by thermal analysis (TG-DTA) and with an
168 elemental analyser. The TG-DTA were performed in a TG Netzsch STA 409PC
169 (Netzsch, Germany). Samples (around 150 mg) were heated in aluminium oxide
170 crucible under a nitrogen atmosphere at 10 °C min⁻¹ from room temperature to
171 1200 °C. Mass losses were measured by TG in the range of temperature 450-
172 900 °C relative to total carbonated decomposition. In the case of the marl, the
173 dehydroxylation of phyllosilicates in this range was taken into account. The
174 elemental carbon contents were measured using an elemental analyser, Truspec
175 CHNS Micro (Leco, Michigan, USA) which calculates the carbonated ratio
176 assuming that the whole carbon content was calcite.

177 The specific surface area (BET), micro- and nano-porosity were measured with
178 an ASAP 2420 (Micromeritics, Georgia, USA) instrument using the adsorption of
179 N₂ at liquid nitrogen temperature (-196 °C) and CO₂ at room temperature. Prior
180 to measurement, all samples were degassed at 150 °C for 180 min and finally
181 outgassed to 10⁻³ Torr. Macro- and meso-porosity were studied using a mercury
182 porosimeter Pore Master 60-GT (Quantachrome Instruments Anton Paar,
183 Austria).

184 Soluble Ca, K, Mg, Si and S ions were measured by a simultaneous inductively
185 coupled plasma - optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) analysis using a
186 ULTIMA 2 (Horiba Jobin Yvon, New York, USA) instrument. The specimens were

187 prepared by mixing the solid powder samples with water and stirring for 24 hours,
188 then concentrating the liquid phase by centrifugation followed by filtering through
189 a Nylon 0.22 μm syringe filter.

190 Micro observations of morphological changes were obtained by scanning
191 electronic microscopy (SEM) using a FEI Teneo microscope.

192 The moisture content of the different sections obtained from the core was
193 measured after heating in an oven at 105 °C for 24 hours.

194

195 **3. Results and discussion**

196 **3.1. Mineralogical carbon sequestration by brick**

197 The XRD patterns of raw and treated samples are displayed in Fig. 2. In all of
198 them, the intensities were normalised to the maximum quartz intensity to provide
199 a more convenient comparison between different patterns. Calcite as a
200 carbonated mineral in brick is evident, as well as the destruction of calcium
201 silicate (wollastonite and diopside), anhydrite and orthoclase. In addition, minor
202 dolomite precipitated and some illite formed probably due to orthoclase alteration.
203 All these changes are consistent with those observed in at previous study carried
204 out with the same brick at 5 months (Martín et al., 2018b).

205

206 Figure 2. XRD patterns of the raw brick (Original at base of figure) and carbonated
207 bricks at different reaction times. Mineral phases: Q (quartz), W (wollastonite),
208 Anh (anhydrite), Plg/FdK (plagioclase and potassium feldspar), Ca (calcite) and I
209 (illite).

210

211 The evolution of mineralogy over time is shown in Table 2 and Fig. 3 shows a
212 representative XRD diffractogram of the Rietveld refinement for C3 (after 9
213 months).

214

215 Table 2. Mineralogy composition of original and treated brick samples (wt%) by
216 Rietveld quantification.

217

218 Figure 3. Representative XRD pattern of C3 showing the presence of calcite as
219 the main carbonated mineral. Observed, calculated, difference and background
220 intensities are displayed (Residual square sum, $R_{wp}=2.95\%$ and possible
221 minimum value for R_{wp} , $R_{exp}=2.22\%$).

222

223 According to the C-elemental and mass loss by TG-DTA results of carbonated
224 samples (Fig. 4) confirms that the process converts the gaseous CO_2 to solid
225 calcium carbonate revealed in X-ray patterns. The most significant growth of CO_2
226 fixed in the bricks took place at 5 months (C1) but remained slightly increasing
227 with longer reaction time in linear trend.

228

229 Figure 4. Carbon and CO_2 content by C-elemental (dash line), CO_2 calculated
230 from C-elemental (dot line) and mass loss by TG-DTA (dash-dot line).

231

232 In terms of BET specific surface area (SSA) evolution (Fig. 5a), there was a
233 decrease from the fresh brick to treated samples. And this SSA decrease directly
234 with time, the main decrease took place in C1 and continue decreasing for long
235 reaction times. This behavior may be due to precipitation of calcium carbonate in
236 micro-pores, creating new nano-porosity as show the CO₂-BET SSA (Fig 5a).
237 Macro- and meso-porosity increased at 5 months. At greater times, macro and
238 meso-porosity decreased but remained above the untreated sample. This
239 increment in meso- and macro-porosity due to carbonated process is produced
240 by the destruction of minerals in the presence of carbonic acid. N₂ adsorption for
241 all treated samples was lower (Fig. 4c), probably related to physical CO₂
242 retention. As for CO₂ adsorption isotherms for C1 at low pressure show that
243 adsorption was higher in original brick than in the carbonated brick, and vice
244 versa at high pressure (Fig. 5d). On the other hand, for the other carbonated
245 samples (C2, C3 and C4), CO₂ adsorption was always above the original value
246 and was greater when the reaction time was greater as consequence of an
247 increase in nano-porosity.

248

249 Figure 5. (a) Specific surface area evolution by N₂-BET and CO₂-BET, (b) meso-
250 and macro-porosity by Hg porosimetry (c) N₂ and (d) CO₂ adsorption isotherms
251 and for original and carbonated samples.

252

253 Neo-formed calcite crystals grown on the brick's surface occur in different habits,
254 such as pseudo-rhombohedral shapes and needles, filling pores. Also, small

255 geometric aggregates of lamellar crystals and dendritic habit can also be
256 observed (Fig. 6).

257

258 Figure 6. Neo-formed calcite crystal on the brick's surface by SEM.

259

260 **3.2. The behavior of sealing marl layer**

261 After the reaction there was a change in the moisture in the bricks and marl. In
262 the bricks the humidity decreased while the marl increased. These variations
263 were greater the longer reaction time. And the longer the reaction time the
264 moisture rose to higher layers of marl. And the longer the humidity reaches higher
265 layers. Likely, all of this was due to the water capillary transport from the brick
266 during the process, favored by the absorption of water by smectites in the marls
267 (Fig. 7a).

268

269 Figure 7. (a) Relative evolution of water content with depth and time reaction
270 (dash-dot line original marl's humidity and dot line for bricks) and (b) CO₂ capture
271 calculated from the carbon content obtained by elementary analysis.

272

273 For all treated samples, the carbonate content increases indicating a higher
274 percentage of CO₂ retained. Broadly, the total calcium and carbon increased,
275 especially in contact with the brick layer, due to a higher quantity of calcium in
276 the marl. According to the mechanisms of carbonation process described above
277 (Eqs. 4 – 9), such increases of carbonate and fluid would be related to the

278 possible transfer of CO₂ on the water and with an external contribution of calcium
279 from the bricks. In terms of temporal variation, the CO₂ capture was greater as
280 the reaction time increased (Fig. 7b). At 5 months (C1) the percentage of CO₂
281 captured was 2 wt% in the layers in contact with the bricks and 1% in the next
282 layer (15-20 cm). For 7 and 9 months (C2 and C3) in these same layers the
283 percentage was 2-2.5 wt% above the bricks, and a slight increase (1.1 wt%) in
284 the bottom marls, as well as in the 12 months' test (C4). In C4 the percentage of
285 CO₂ captured was from 2.5 to 3 wt% in the clayey materials up to 15 cm deep,
286 however, unlike the other tests the upper layers to this were reached up to 1 wt%.

287 In marls, N₂-BET specific surface area was higher (Fig. 8a) than the original
288 value. Therefore, there was not a significant variation of in marls for the different
289 reaction times, beyond a slightly increased. This increase could be related to a
290 possible destruction or alteration of the mineralogy of the clay, creating new
291 specific surface and micro-porosity. In contrast, CO₂-BET specific surface area
292 was higher after de treatment but it was smaller the longer the reaction time (Fig.
293 8b) due to the carbonate precipitation. In the latter, the CO₂ adsorption isotherms
294 (Fig. 7d) show less volume adsorbed over all ranges of pressure than the original
295 sample. Nonetheless, the N₂ isotherm remained constant (Fig. 8c). Both, CO₂-
296 BET and CO₂ adsorption behaviors could be related to physical retention in
297 micro- and nano-pores and/or due to the carbonate precipitation covering/filling
298 pores.

299

300 Figure 8. (a) Specific surface area evolution by N₂-BET and (b) CO₂-BET, (c) N₂
301 and (d) CO₂ adsorption isotherms and for original and closer layer (20- 25 cm)
302 for C1 and C4.

303

304 Soluble calcium ions (Fig. 9a) of the marl decreased in the first 5 cm above the
305 brick layer for C1 and C2 but not under the brick, related to de carbonated
306 precipitation too. In the rest of the sections, soluble calcium was around the
307 original marl content. In C3 and C4, calcium increased and these increases were
308 higher closer to the bricks. Therefore, calcium was available for further
309 precipitation. On the other hand, potassium (Fig. 9b) increased for all reactions
310 10 cm closer to bricks with no variation in shallower layers. There was not an
311 important variation of magnesium and silicon. Sulfur in solution (Fig. 9c) was
312 concentrated close to the brick layer and especially at the bottom preventing
313 sulfur escape to the surface. The sulfur originated from anhydrite destruction. On
314 the other hand, in the layer above the bricks more sulfur accumulated over time.
315 In the layer below the situation was the opposite, and may be due to the formation
316 of sulfates as alunite.

317

318 Figure 9. (a) Calcium, (b) potassium and (c) sulfur soluble ions content.

319

320 This same behavior, especially in the case of calcite, is observed in the total
321 elemental analysis (Table 3). The increase in the total calcium content in the marl
322 in the layers close to the bricks with respect to their original value together with
323 the decrease in the bricks treated with respect to the original confirm the migration

324 of calcium from the brick to the marl. In addition, the total magnesium followed to
325 calcium, but the precipitation of magnesium carbonate phases was not observed.
326 The increase in LOI confirmed the presence of carbonates.

327

328 Table 3. Chemical composition of original and treated sample after 5 and 12
329 months of reaction by XRF; normalized at 100 wt%.

330

331 As with the bricks, in the surfaces in the marls grew new calcite in different habits,
332 however the new crystals were of smaller size probably because the marls
333 present a more irregular, more porous surface, impeding crystal to greater sizes
334 (Fig. 10).

335

336 Figure 10. New calcite crystal on the marl's surface by SEM.

337

338 In summary, wollastonite and anhydrite, the main calcium sources were
339 destroyed in the brick layer and subsequently calcite precipitation occurred. At 5
340 months this destruction is very significant as shown by the X-ray patterns (Fig.
341 2). Nevertheless, the relative intensity of the (1 0 4) reflection of the calcite
342 increased with longer reaction time, due to an increase of calcite content and thus
343 an increase in carbon dioxide captured (Fig. 3). In marls, the most significant
344 mineral modification occurred in smectite. The total CO₂ capture at 5 months was
345 around 17 wt% and 12 months was around 23 wt% (Table 4).

346

347 Table 4. Total CO₂ capture (wt%) and in different layers (calculated by C-
348 elemental less the original value).

349

350 The evolution of the different porosity scales show that the carbonation process
351 takes place in two distinct steps: a) the mineral destruction by the action of
352 carbonic acid producing an irregular surface and an increase in of macro- and
353 meso-porosity; and b) the precipitation of carbonates filling the micro-pores and
354 as a consequence an increase of nano-porosity. Also, physical retention of CO₂
355 was observed.

356

357 **4. Conclusions**

358 The behavior of the brick layer within the reaction time indicated that major
359 destruction of mineral phases took place rapidly (5 months). And, this increase in
360 time produced a reduction of porous size.

361 The response of marls depends on the reaction time and the origin of carbonation
362 precipitated is the Ca²⁺ and CO₃²⁻ dissolved in water that arrived at higher levels
363 by capillarity.

364 The designed system, that would mimic the reclamation of a quarry filled with
365 bricks and with marl as sealing material, was run satisfactorily, fixing the CO₂ as
366 calcite in the brick and in the marls. These results open the opportunity to use
367 these wastes for CO₂ sequestration in a real quarry reclamation.

368

369

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377

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543

544 **Appendix A. Supplementary data**

545

546 Table S1. Carbon content by elemental analyser, mass loss by thermogravimetry,
547 N₂ and CO₂ specific surface area by BET and Ca, K, Mg, Si and S soluble ions
548 evolution in the original and treated samples.

549

550 **List of tables and figures:**

551 Table 1. Granulometric fractions of the crusher sample (wt%).

552 Table 2. Mineralogy composition of original and treated brick samples (wt%) by
553 Rietveld quantification.

554 Table 3. Chemical composition of original and treated sample after 5 and 12
555 months of reaction by XRF; normalized at 100 wt%.

556 Table 4. Total CO₂ capture (wt%) and in different layers (calculated by C-
557 elemental less the original value).

558

559 Figure 1. Scheme of the reaction chamber designed for CO₂ brick reaction. The
560 brick layer is yellow and the marl is light gray (front view) and sampling cores at
561 5, 7, 9 and 12 months (top view).

562 Figure 2. XRD patterns of the raw brick (Original in red) and carbonated bricks at
563 different reaction times. Mineral phases: Q (quartz), W (wollastonite), Anh
564 (anhydrite), Plg/FdK (plagioclase and potassium feldspar), Ca (calcite) and I
565 (illite).

566 Figure 3. Representative XRD pattern of C3 showing the presence of calcite as
567 the main carbonated mineral. Observed, calculated, difference and background
568 intensities are displayed (Residual square sum, Rwp=2.95% and possible
569 minimum value for Rwp, Rexp=2.22%).

570 Figure 4. Carbon and CO₂ content by C-elemental (dash line), CO₂ calculated
571 from C-elemental (dot line) and mass loss by TG-DTA (dash-dot line).

572 Figure 5. (a) Specific surface area evolution by N₂-BET and CO₂-BET, (b) meso-
573 and macro-porosity by Hg porosimetry (c) N₂ and (d) CO₂ adsorption isotherms
574 and for original and carbonated samples.

575 Figure 6. Neo-formed calcite crystal on the brick's surface by SEM.

576 Figure 7. (a) Relative humidity evolution with depth and time reaction (dash-dot
577 line original marl's humidity and dot line for bricks) and (b) CO₂ capture calculated
578 from the carbon content obtained by elementary analysis.

579 Figure 8. (a) Specific surface area evolution by N₂-BET and (b) CO₂-BET, (c) N₂
580 and (d) CO₂ adsorption isotherms and for original and closer layer (20- 25 cm)
581 for C1 and C4.

582 Figure 9. (a) Calcium, (b) potassium and (c) sulfur soluble ions content.

583 Figure 10. New calcite crystal on the marl's surface by SEM.

584